

A NOVEL DESIGN OF A SAMPLE AND HOLD CIRCUIT UTILIZING COMPOSITE OP AMPS

Sherif Michael and Patrick Gariano, Jr.

Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey, CA 93943

ABSTRACT

Recently a technique for designing high-speed, high accuracy Operational Amplifiers (op amps) was proposed by the authors. The technique was based on the composite operational amplifier structures that were known for their excellent AC and DC characteristics. In this contribution preliminary results of a novel sample and hold circuit is presented. The results clearly show the considerable improvement when the high-speed, high-accuracy op amps were used in constructing the sample and hold circuit. The circuit would be capable of providing precise output at a very high sampling rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's technology, signal processing is more and more often accomplished using digital methods. Since most of the events occurring in the physical world we live in are analog by nature, the desire to process information digitally requires a conversion of the analog signal into a digital one, and often after processing, from digital back to analog. Central to such systems are sample and hold circuits.

Sample and hold circuits are widely used in analog signal processing and data conversion systems to store an analog voltage precisely over a different period of time. This capability allowed them to be suitable for numerous applications including data multiplexing systems, data acquisition systems, simultaneous sample and hold systems, A/D converter front ends, signal reconstruction filters and analog computers. [1,2]

A sample and hold circuit is basically a voltage memory device that stores a given analog voltage on a high quality capacitor. The circuit can sample an analog signal at a given instant of time and then freeze it as long as the system requires. Fig. 1 shows a fundamental sample and hold circuit. A_1 is an input buffer amplifier with a high input impedance so that the source is not loaded. The output of A_1 must be capable of driving the hold capacitor with stability and enough drive current to charge it rapidly. S_1 is an electronically controlled switch, often a MOSFET device, which provides a means for

rapidly charging the capacitor to the sampled voltage and then isolating the input voltage source from the circuit so that the capacitor can store the desired input voltage level. C is a capacitor with low leakage and low dielectric absorption properties, normally polycarbonate, polypropylene or teflon type. In the case of hybrid sample and hold, MOS capacitors are used. A_2 is the output amplifier which buffers the voltage on the hold capacitor. It must therefore have extremely low input bias current (often FET input OP AMP is used).

In addition to the basic sample and hold circuit of Fig. 1, there are several other configurations which are frequently used. Fig. 2 illustrates some of the closed loop sample and hold circuits, which are used for different applications.

To abide with the sampling theorem, and in order for the sample and hold circuit to produce a good approximation of the input waveform being sampled, it is necessary for the frequency of the switch "clocking" control to be substantially higher than that of the input signal. This dictates a certain requirement on the components used in the design. High speed op amps would appear essential in such case, since lower slew rate components would introduce major errors. To get a better understanding of further requirements that might be imposed upon such a circuit to minimize other sources of errors, it is necessary to visualize the circuit in conjunction with a state-of-the-art A/D converter. Since the sample and hold circuit would be the front end of such an A/D converter, and assuming a 16 bit digital system it can be easily shown that the size of the least significant bit would be $153 \mu\text{V}$ for a 10 volt maximum analog input. To achieve such accuracy the use of high precision components would become apparent.

In this research application of the high-speed, high-accuracy op amps, introduced earlier by the authors [3-5], will be demonstrated in developing a novel sample and hold circuit design.

2. HIGH-SPEED, HIGH-ACCURACY OP AMPS:

Theoretical constraints encountered in the design of op amps have precluded the fabrication of a single op amp capable of

simultaneously providing both high speed and high accuracy. Previous papers presented by the authors [3,4] have discussed these limitations and recounted some of the more successful methods utilized to enhance op amp performances. But in each case in which a substantial enhancement of slew rate was achieved, a penalty of a concomitant degradation in the input offset voltage and drift as well as some degradation in noise performance was paid. However, since in many applications (e.g. sample and hold circuits), the need for accurate, offset free amplifiers is as important as the need for fast ones, researchers efforts have continued in search for common solution.

Recently a technique was introduced by the authors in [4] using a composite op amps to combine "the best of both worlds". Utilizing a very accurate op amp and a very fast one to generate a composite that has speeds and accuracies on the order of or greater than its parent counterparts. Several families of composite op amps (CNOAs) were originally developed in [6]. These CNOAs were well known for their wide bandwidth and dynamic range, insensitivity to components, power supply variations and Gain Bandwidth Product (GBWP) mismatch, stability etc. Improved active realizations performance, relative to the state-of-the-art designs using a similar number of op amps has been demonstrated in a wide range of signal processing applications, when the CNOAs were used to replace the regular op amps. In these proposed CNOA families, the fact that mismatching of the individual op amp's GBWPs is tolerated, provided an excellent chance to construct CNOAs tailored to certain specifications.

Four designs of high-speed, high accuracy op amps were introduced in [4] based on one family of CNOA shown in Fig. 3. In these designs using a precision op amp (HA-5170 that contributes little DC error) in place of A_1 in any of the C20As, provided excellent front-end characteristics for the composite. Similarly choosing a high slew-rate, fast settling, and wide bandwidth op amp (ex HA-2525) as the output op amp in place of A_2 resulted in a fast output stage.

Analysis of the above design showed that the resulting composite amplifier enjoyed essentially the same excellent resolution and high accuracy of the precision op amp used in the front end. This is true since the effect of the non-precision output op amp is drastically reduced at the front-end of any of the C20As, as shown in Table 1. Similarly, it was found that the limitation of the slew rate and bandwidth of the front-end op amp had very little effect on the high-speed performance of the resulting composite amplifier. This is also true, since it can be easily shown that the voltage swing at the A_1 op amp output, which is an internal node in each of the C20As, is always much less than the output voltage

swing. Thus no dynamic range reduction or harmonic distortion should arise due to the limited power bandwidth of the front-end op amp. This indicated that the high-speed performance of the composite op amp is very much similar to that of the fast op amp used in the output stage.

These hypothesis were clearly demonstrated in the experimental results of the high-speed, high-accuracy amplifiers shown in Tables 2-5 for the four C20As. Applications of these novel designs in linear and non-linear active networks [5], demonstrated clearly the superiority of these designs, and the possible dramatic improvement that these designs may contribute to sample and hold circuits.

3. THE NOVEL SAMPLE AND HOLD CIRCUITS:

As with most practical sample and hold circuits, op amps are employed by the circuit to present a low driving circuit impedance and a high load impedance across the capacitor as shown in Fig. 1, 2. For many critical applications, the utilization of precision, high speed op amps are essential for developing an optimum design with minimum sources of errors.

Considering the case discussed earlier where an accurate, high speed sample and hold circuit were needed as a front end of the 16-bit A/D converter, with accuracy better than $153 \mu\text{V}$. The results shown in Tables 2-5 indicated that the slew rate and input offset voltages achieved by the HA-5170/HA-2525 combination in the C20A-1, C20A-3 or C20A-4 configurations would fulfill the requirements, i.e. an LSB size of $153 \mu\text{V}$ and a very high clock rate. Rather than using two composite op amp structures to construct any of the sample and hold circuits of Fig. 2, it was found that a single high-speed, high accuracy composite op amp with a CMOS switch and a storage capacitor can perform as well (and in some cases better) than two composite configurations.

Fig. 4 shows the novel sample and hold circuit constructed utilizing the C20A-3 with $\alpha=0.43$ and $k=2.0$. The placement of the capacitor between the switch and the non-inverting terminal of the HA-2525 was selected such that during the hold periods, the capacitor would not be able to discharge due to the open switch on one side and the high input impedance of the 2525 on the other.

Fig. 5 shows the preliminary results obtained for this circuit. Here the input analog signal was a 100 kHz sinusoid. The switching control voltage (vs) was applied at a frequency of 2.6 MHz (sampling rate). The photograph shows both the input and the sampled output waveforms intentionally offset. It clearly demonstrates that the circuit amplified the signal by a factor of two ($K=2$), and was able to sample at the 2.6 MHz clocking rate; i.e. -26 samples per cycle, with no sign of distortion or noise.

The results do not represent the upper limits of this novel design. The clocking rates and α and k parameters were chosen merely to illustrate the utility of the circuit and that it would perform adequately in a demanding situation. Higher clock rates are quite likely permissible and better results may have been achievable with the other, more accurate and faster configuration.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this research the preliminary results of a novel sample and hold circuit is presented. The design was based on the optimum high-speed, high accuracy composite amplifiers that were developed earlier by the authors. The proposed sample and hold circuit has demonstrated a significantly improved AC and DC performance over currently available state-of-the-arts monolithic designs [7]. While some of the results are reported, work is in progress for the development of the optimum structures for maximum speed and accuracy as well as investigating the improvement of other sample and hold parameters.

5. REFERENCES

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C20A-1	$V_{\text{off}} \approx V_{\text{off1}} + (V_{\text{off2}}/\alpha)$
C20A-2	$V_{\text{off}} = V_{\text{off1}} + (V_{\text{off2}}/A_1)$
C20A-3	$V_{\text{off}} = V_{\text{off1}} + [V_{\text{off2}}(1 + \alpha)/A_1]$
C20A-4	$V_{\text{off}} = V_{\text{off1}} + [V_{\text{off2}}(1 + \alpha)/(A_1 + \alpha)]$

Table 1 Effect of individual OA's offset voltage on the C20As input offset voltage.

C20A-1						
OA #1	OA #2	α	K	SLEW RATE (V/ μ S)	V_{off}	GBWP
741	2525	1.0	88.0	23.8		64 MHz
2505	2505	2.0	1.0	41.7		
2525	2525	4.0	54.0	167		231 MHz
5170	2525	0	11.8	117.6	60 μ V	49.5 MHz
5170	2525	1.0	15.0	104.2		55.7 MHz

Table 2 The High-Speed, High-Accuracy C20A-1 Parameters Using Different Op Amps.

C20A-2						
OA #1	OA #2	α	K	SLEW RATE	GBWP	
741	741	15.8	9.7	0.96		
2505	2505	1.0	9.7	33.3		
2525	2525	4.0	40.0	133		235 MHz

Table 3 The High-Speed, High-Accuracy C20A-2 Parameters Using Different Op Amps.

C20A-3						
OA #1	OA #2	α	K	SLEW RATE (V/ μ S)	V_{off}	GBWP
741	741	2.0	10.7	0.96		
2505	2505	2.0	1.0	34.5		
5170	2525	0.43	1.8	142.8	123 μ V	10.4 MHz

Table 3 The High-Speed, High-Accuracy C20A-3 Parameters Using Different Op Amps.

C20A-4

OA #1	OA #2	α	K	SLEW RATE (V/ μ S)	V_{off}	CBWP
741	741	2.0	9.7	0.96		
2505	2505	1.0	1.0	33.3		
2525	2525	4.8	3.0	167.0		34 MHz
5170	2525	3.3	11.3	142.9	53 μ V	35 MHz
2525	5170	19.5	2.0		6.7 mV	
2525	2539	5.0	2.8	714.2		
5170	2539	5.0	7.0	555.6		
5170	2525	10.0	1.5	190.5		

RECALL	S.R.	V_{off}	CBWP
741	0.85		
2505	35		
2525	140	6.68 mV	23.1 MHz
2539	715		
5170	8	121 μ V	4.6 MHz

Table 4 The High-Speed, High-Accuracy C20A-4 Parameters Using Different Op Amps, and the Individual Op Amps Parameters.

Fig. 1 The Fundamental Sample and Hold Circuit.

Fig. 2

Different Closed-Loop Sample and Hold Configurations.

Fig. 3 The Composite Operational Amplifiers C20As.

Fig. 4 Novel Sample & Hold Circuit

Fig. 5 Preliminary experimental results
 $f_{signal} = 100\text{KHz}$ & $f_{clock} = 2.6\text{MHz}$